

English as a Global Language

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Abstract:

Communication is an essential skill that forms the backbone of human interaction. From personal to global enterprises, communication is very significant for progress and success. Language is a mode of communication. Language is shaped by various factors like history, geography, politics and culture. According to recent research there are more than seven thousand languages across the globe. In this number of languages some languages have only spoken form without a script. In 21st Century there are two billion people communicate in English as their first language, second or third language. English is considered as the significant language globally in the fields of science, business, films, music, academics, technologies and literature. It is a language that enables us to bridge the gap between people from different countries. A vast number of books, newspapers, magazines in the globe are written in English. In human history there is no such single language spoken so widely across the globe. Today English has become significant part of our lives.

Keywords: Communication, languages, English language, Global language. Future.

This paper is an attempt to present English as Global Language. It also analyses how and why English became international and global language. Further paper also explores the scope, development and features of English as a global language. The paper concludes with future of English language as global language. Man is social animal. He cannot live in society without communicating. He wants to share his ideas, opinions with his community. Before language came to be used as a means of communication primitive men used body language to express his/her feelings. Language is a mode of communication. Language has been shaped by various factors like history, geography, culture, custom. There are more than 7000 languages across the world. All these languages have had their natural growth along with the progress and

formation of the community. All natural languages have had their origin in speech.

Global Language:

The term 'Global' may refers to constructed international auxiliary languages. There is no official definition of 'global language' or "world language", but it essentially refers to a language that is learned and spoken internationally, and is characterized not only by the number of its native and second language speakers, but also geographical distribution, and its use in international organizations and in diplomatic relations. A global language acts as a "lingua franca", a common language that enables people from diverse backgrounds A global language is one that is spoken and understood by a large number of people on a worldwide scale. A global language or a world language is a language

that is geographically widespread and makes it possible for members of different language communities to communicate. A global language allows communication between different cultures. According to linguist, Salikoko Mufwene " a global language is spoken as vernaculars or as lingua francas outside their homelands and by populations other than those ethnically or nationally associated with them". The global language can be spoken as either first, second or third language. The significant salient feature of a global language is that it is the most widely used language in communication in most places in the world. People feel the need to master it for their life. According to David Crystals a language can achieve its role as a global language when it reaches and accepted in every country. He further mentions that there are two main ways to make a language global. He claims that a global language can be chosen to be used as first or second language in a country and it should be used in all kinds of communication, in technology, academic, science and in government.

English as a global language: English is the most popular and significant language spoken in almost all countries. According to recent survey, nearly half of the world's population is well-versed in this language. English is an efficient language worldwide. Compared to other world's languages, English is easier to learn and teach. Today nearly two billion people communicate in English, as their first, second or third language. The role of English language as global language has been expanded over the past few centuries. English has become the primary means of communication in international trade, technology, education. People need to speak English if they wish to enter a global workforce. Learning and speaking English language increases one's chances of getting hired and provides with greater opportunities to enhance career. Now a days more and more companies

and industries in all over the world are mandating English as the official corporate language. Number of books, academic research papers, periodicals, magazine and news in the world are written in English. In present century English maintains its dominant position as the primary language used in global business transactions. English is the language of international contracts, negotiations, financial markets and business communication. Many multinational corporations use English as their primary mode of communication within their global networks. As of 2025, there are 58 sovereign states and 28 non-sovereign entities where English is an official language. John Adam, great leader of the late eighteenth century made the following insightful prophecy --- "English will be the most respectable language in the world and the most universally read and spoken in the next century."

How English became Global:

The influence of British history, as well as cultural, economics, technological and social factors contributed to the spread of English across the globe. The British Empire and rise of the United States helped establish English as a dominant global language. The British Empire's expansion across the world made English the language of commerce in many countries. The British Empire, had more colonies than any other country in human history, including New Zealand, India and the United States. It was described as "the British Empire on which the sun never sets." By 1913, nearly 23% of the world's population lived on the territory of the British rule. Although these countries, colonies got their independence they accepted English language. The British Empire's vast reach (covering a quarter of the world by the 19th century) introduced English to diverse populations in North America, India, Africa and Australia. By the 18th century, the British Empire had spread

English through its colonies. Science, technology and commerce are contributed to English becoming its first truly global language. English became the language for colonial governance, law and higher education. In 20th century, the United State of America, especially after World War II became a major political superpower. The world after war was a vulnerable and changing world. American companies were spread and began to trade all over the world, as Britain in 18th and 19th centuries. This result in English language as dominant language in trade. Its became language of trades.

English language is spoken by the largest population in the world. The largest number of English speakers is in countries like Canada, Australia, United Kingdom and the United States. English is used as a means of communication in various contexts such as government, the law courts, the media, and the educational system. The 21st century has witnessed a revolution in the use of Internets, mobiles and Emails.

English is considered as one of the easier languages to learn. It has simple grammatical structure. English also adopted a significant amount of vocabulary from different languages. For many new English learners around the world it is an easy language. In number of countries English introduced in primary schools. It is learned at an early age. The free online sources, language apps, number of learning tools made teaching and learning English more accessible.

Emphasizing English language' role in modern world Late Prime Minister of India Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru called English as a 'window to the world.' English acts as a global gateway, providing access to vast knowledge, opportunities, and connections in education, technology, culture and business. It's the primary language for international communication, research and the internet. It allows people to see

and interact with diverse global developments and information.

English language is a gateway to careers. In the world of globalization, English language significant as global language. It provides multiple opportunities in various sectors. It also provides understanding various fields since most of the information is available in only English. As the language of commerce, education, academia and international communication English has become significant. Widespread use of English made it as bridge of communication. Books, magazines, and newspapers written in English are available in many countries around the world, and English is the most commonly used language in the sciences and literatures. Recent report of 1997 shows that 95% of its articles were written in English, even though only half of them came from authors in English-speaking countries.

English language plays important role in travel and tourism .As travel and tourism is related to both national and international levels, English is the language that is commonly used by all the international travel and tourism departments, agencies and companies. To travel to a foreign country, one must know the language of the others to communicate with the people of that country.

In the field of press and media, English is used as the primary language of the world due to the fact that it is the language used internationally by a majority of speakers. There are some television channels such as Discovery, Animal Planet, National Geographic, etc. help the learners improve their English. There is a lot of impact of the media as well as the press on the young generation learners of English and most of them follow these English channels to improve their language skills.

English has become a cultural bridge between different countries and cultures. English-language literature, movies, and music have

gained global popularity, leading to cross-cultural exchanges and the spread of cultural awareness.

English language is the significant language that unites people of different nations. English stands as the dominant force in science, literature, culture, economics and politics. Learning English opens doors to career, advancement, and international mobility. It provides access to global markets and technical innovation.

Following are some features of English Language.

- Compared to other languages of the world English is richest in vocabulary.
- Compared to other languages of the world English is widely spoken and written.
- For Internet and social media English used throughout the world.
- It is used in international organizations such as the United Nations, where it is one of the six official languages,
- In the field of press and media, English is used as the primary language of the world.
- It serves as the common language for multinational companies and is an official language for global institutions.
- English acts as a universal bridge for travellers and cultural exchange, enabling communication in diverse countries and providing access to global media.
- English is the medium of huge information stored in the computers.
- English is crucial for higher education, with many universities using it as the medium of instruction.
- English language opens door to better jobs and global career prospects.
- **English language has historical Legacy and Colonization.**
- **English is a language of Science and Technology.**

- **English is language used in Cultural Export and Media.**
- English is used as an official or semi-official language in over 60 countries,
- It is the universal language that is used in the field of education, technology, medicine, entertainment, diplomacy, computing etc
- It is the only language that truly links the whole world together.
- It is one of the most significant languages in the world.
- It is used globally for speaking as well as writing.
- It is a recognised official language in most of the countries.
- In the present era, English is considered to be the language of the common man.
- English has become a bridge language connecting people from different countries and cultures.
- English is the primary language for academic publishing, scientific research, and international education.
- Many top universities worldwide offer programs in English, attracting students from different linguistic backgrounds.
- English has become a language of diplomacy and international relations

As its accessibility, and widespread as a second and third language in number of countries it continues to attract masses. Its significance will continue to grow. It has been suggested that the English language will provide the key to economic prosperity of the world in future. English will no doubt remain an important asset in terms of the production and marketing of intellectual property. There is no other language appear within the next fifty years to replace English as global language. The position of

English has arisen from a particular history which no other language can. English is globally accepted and known by all. The number of people using English is growing day by day. English is the most common language that is spoken everywhere. So, its role in the global world can't be denied

Conclusion:

Thus English is a global language used by billions worldwide. It is primary language useful in international business, technology, science. English language provides access to vast resources of knowledge, information. It provides the route of bridging cultures and connecting the world. It is taught as foreign language in more than 100 countries. English is not only language

but it is key to a world of opportunities and information.

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